

Workshop summary report

May 2-3, 2022 - Towards an open atlas of knowledge for invasion biology and beyond!

We were very happy to welcome ca. 90 participants to this first online workshop. We had quite a diverse group of people, with regards to gender, position, geographical location, and even expertise, which ranged beyond invasion ecology to include urban ecology, restoration ecology or philosophy of science. Half of participants were permanent researchers, and gender balance was slightly biased towards men (55.5%). Unsurprisingly given our network of colleagues, over 71% of participants are currently working in Europe, with 23% in Germany and 10% in the UK. Due in part to time zones, the American continent was also over-represented (23%) compared to Asia (<1%), Africa (4%, all from South Africa), or Oceania, which was entirely absent.

Current position

Main fields of expertise

First day: presentation of projects and tools

The first day consisted of presentations from the different partners of the enKORE and INAS projects.

1. Overview of the project

Jonathan Jeschke first introduced [Hi Knowledge](#), an initiative to synthesize and visualize scientific knowledge, which he started over a decade ago with Tina Heger. Tina then presented the two current Hi Knowledge projects: the enKORE project, aiming to provide tools for the community to navigate scientific knowledge and literature in invasion biology, and the [INAS project](#), focussing on more fundamental aspects of building ontologies and argumentation machines to model hypotheses in Invasion biology. Crucial issues were brought up immediately in the first round of questions, and often further discussed throughout the workshop.

We discussed first the need for **an entirely open infrastructure**, relying on open data and softwares, and therefore bypassing existing proprietary tools like the Web of Science. The tools we develop would also go far beyond the type of data currently handled by these bibliometric databases.

A second crucial point which immediately came up was: **how would this tool and database be kept up-to-date?** The answer, as we saw during the rest of the workshop, is a combination of machine learning and manual curation by the community.

A more philosophical concern regarding the project was to question **the risk of guiding people too much** towards existing knowledge and hypotheses, instead of allowing chaos to promote exploration and innovation. We agreed that some measure of chaos was still

wanted, and would always remain. This tool would be only one additional tool in the toolkit available for researchers, and could not serve every purpose. It might nevertheless help innovation by revealing knowledge gaps.

Finally, some participants wondered whether these tools would **allow us to connect scientists working on the same topic** (taxa, etc.) but in different geographic ranges (e.g. native vs. introduced range), or perhaps more generally help us find the right people for a particular question. Currently, this is not yet a feature we are implementing, but it could be a potential addition in the future, in particular via Wikidata/Scholia, which already offers an entry point to the database via author networks, geographical locations and main topics of research.

2. Open Knowledge Maps

Peter Kraker, chairman and founder of [Open Knowledge Maps](#) (OKMaps), presented the OKMaps project, and what they are currently implementing for the enKORE project. OKMaps is an online tool creating visual representations of literature searches. Relying on databases such as PubMed and BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine), the software uses natural language processing of titles and abstracts, combined with ordination methods (e.g. NMDS), to aggregate and display publications according to similarity in topics. For the enKORE project, the OKMaps team is customizing the tool, visualization and database for invasion biology publications.

Questions for Peter concerned the **problem of using the “relevance” metric**, as calculated by bibliometric databases like PubMed, to select for the subset of 100 papers used to build the map. This metric is known to be biased towards recent papers. A second point was the problem of **filtering search results precisely and accurately**, which, if it could be improved, would already greatly reduce the figurative wave of publications we are drowning under.

A lively discussion in the chat (copied in the Slack workspace) followed concerning **how to identify the most “relevant” papers** in a literature search, and how this would mean different things whether one is aiming to understand the background of a topic, or scanning for new developments. Problems with using the number of citations as a criteria was debated: perhaps it can capture the “usefulness” of a publication, but then it has such a strong “social signal” that it is likely too biased to be relevant. Some wondered about the possibility of identifying “classic”, or foundational, papers, and Peter Kraker commented that this was “the million dollar question”, likely answerable only by a combination of AI and expert curation. As an example of how this could appear in our tools, Tina mentioned that key papers had been identified for urban ecology hypotheses and are available on the corresponding [urban ecology Wikidata project page](#).

3. Wikidata and Scholia

Daniel Mitchen, biophysicist and data analyst focusing on Wikimedia tools for the enKORE project, presented how [Wikidata](#) and [Scholia](#) are contributing to the Hi Knowledge initiative. Wikidata is a massive aggregator of open data, including bibliometric data, providing the basis for a large corpus of literature. This corpus can then be openly annotated and organized according to topics both by the community and by half automated SPARQL

queries which the community can design. Scholia then offers a navigational tool to visualize and summarize Wikidata information according to authors, regions, taxa, topics, etc.

Daniel shared example Scholia profiles for:

- A taxon as a topic: *Apis mellifera*, <https://scholia.toolforge.org/topic/Q30034>.
- An invasive taxon as a taxon: *Phragmites australis*, <https://scholia.toolforge.org/taxon/Q28557>
- An invasion biology variable as a topic: **Invasion Success**, <https://scholia.toolforge.org/topic/Q109467185>

Wikidata allows to create thematic “projects”, and an overview of the current enKORE project efforts is provided by the Invasion biology WikiProject:

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Invasion_biology . In the breakout sessions, profiles of participants as well as of topics related to urban ecology were also shared, and curation workflows were demoed.

4. Open Knowledge Research Graphs (ORKG)

Markus Stocker, Head of the Knowledge Infrastructures Research Group at the TIB (Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Hannover, Germany), presented the [ORKG project](#), which he co-leads. The ORKG project aims **to digitize scientific literature** in a way that “unpacks” studies out of their pdf or paper formats, and **make them machine readable** to enable searching and meta-analysis of data and results. This open project relies on manual curation by users, in particular the contribution of detailed metadata, data and standardized results to describe each publication. For the enKORE project, an [Invasion Biology Observatory](#) has been set up, which will gather all contributions related to invasion biology. They are developing **a template specifically tailored for invasion biology** to guide the manual contribution of publications and results in the field.

As an example, publications testing 12 major hypotheses in invasion biology have already been contributed based on previous work in the Hi-Knowledge initiative. Studies can be grouped and compared, as in this example for the enemy release hypothesis: <https://www.orkg.org/orkg/comparison/R58002/>. Further on-demand interactive analyses of the results across studies will be possible via online tools such as Jupyter notebooks (cf. Break-out group discussions on the second day). In addition, “Review” project pages can be created in ORKG, which can group comparisons and analyses, as well as add further text commentary (example review for [Smart City Ontologies](#)). Similarly to Wikidata project pages, these are entirely manually curated by a community of users.

In a following Q&A session, **the question of the quality and reliability of publications** was raised. Can we have criteria evaluating the quality of publications aggregated by our suite of tools? What if we are synthesizing a mix of good and bad studies? It appears for now that quality assessments can only rely on the community of experts, but this is not really happening due to low engagement. Participants were also concerned about **possible biases in the literature synthesized**, and how these could be addressed in the tools. Finally, the question of **community engagement** was identified as a major issue. One suggestion was to **make it compulsory when submitting a manuscript to a journal** for authors to provide

detailed and standardized paper annotations. Jonathan mentioned that this was being discussed with the journal *NeoBiota*.

Synthesis of break out group discussions

Over 50 participants engaged in group discussions on the second day. Based on participants' interests, we included an additional group on the question of meta-analyses and data synthesis, while the topic of funding (for early career positions and synthesis projects) was suggested as an additional topic for future meetings.

In summary, we can identify a few take-away points:

1. Defining the community's needs and wishes:

- We identified **key characteristics of papers** that will be useful for navigation, filtering of searches, and organization of the literature in invasion biology and beyond (cf. [Table 1](#)). We will use this list to design a template for modeling and entering the data in ORKG and Wikidata. Potentially, this template for modeling the data could serve as an example for a submission checklist in journals (e.g. *NeoBiota*).
- **Including grey literature and dealing with different languages** would be important, in particular for queries concerning management. This is not yet implemented explicitly, but Wikidata may perhaps provide a solution, as it already offers multiple language integration and aggregates all sorts of literature.

2. Overall feedback on the project:

- **Community engagement and manual contributions are a major bottleneck.** How to overcome this:
 - Usefulness would have to be clear for the users and contributors.
 - Create incentives for contributors?
 - Make it mandatory when submitting a manuscript?
 - Manual curation (of ORKG or Wikidata) should be made easy and streamlined (e.g. with guided templates and examples). The difficulty will be to balance genericity with flexibility of the manual contribution framework.
 - Early career researchers may be the most interested in contributing data and time to such open knowledge efforts
- **Automation methods are not very clear to many participants.** Designing ontologies and connecting tools in a transparent way appeared as desirable but difficult to understand for most people.

3. Building a community and expanding the project to other fields:

The workshop was an important step towards building a community, and in addition to invasion biology, we have started to expand the project to the fields of restoration ecology and urban ecology, and have made more concrete plans for an extension towards

freshwater biodiversity research, here in collaboration with the [Alliance for Freshwater Life](#).

Next steps

A second workshop is planned for 2023 (dates TBA), hopefully in a hybrid (virtual and physical presence) format, during which we will present our progress based on the feedback we received in this first workshop, and participants will be able to further try out the tools. In the meantime, all participants will be invited to provide additional feedback and to participate in focused discussions and presentations in the next 12 months. We are hoping that following this first workshop, the participants will form the foundation for a community of contributors and users for our tools.

Table 1. Characteristics of papers to filter and organize literature searches

Study characteristics	Description and example	Particular issues?	Why is it useful?	Mentioned in break out groups
Basic bibliographic traits				
Article/Publication identifier and content	Automation requires persistent identifiers, preferably DOI; having some additional bibliographic metadata helps with curation	OK Maps needs access to abstracts and/ or full text (PDF/ HTML/ XML), for which Wikidata needs licensing information	we use the papers as the basic unit of building the invasion biology corpus	Wikidata
Authors	List of names and affiliations Ideally with information about author order (first, middle and last authors)	Having unique identifiers and standardizing names. ORCID would help. Most helpful would be an identifier that allows retrieving more information on the authors as needed (e.g. research field, career status)	Identifying invasion biologists vs. other ecologists to help define the scope Identifying senior scientists/leading scientists = an entry point for early career Author co-authorship networks/citation networks to identify communities of researchers	Wikidata Early career
Journal	Name of journal	ISSN	Journal reputation informs trustworthiness of paper Finding papers within a given scope/research context or field	Early career
Citations	Number of citations	Different counts according to reference (WoK, Google scholar...). Needs to be constantly updated automatically.	Useful for early career to assess relevance	Early career

Study characteristics	Description and example	Particular issues?	Why is it useful?	Mentioned in break out groups
Type of paper	Or Article category: review, meta-analyses, original research, opinion paper, perspective paper, methods paper...	Not always tagged in/by the journals?	Reviews and opinion papers are useful to get acquainted with state of the art and research gaps Filtering out secondary analyses when extracting papers for a meta-analyses	Early career Meta-analyses
Useful characteristics				
Habitat	Habitat, or habitats, investigated in the study. May need to allow for multiple entries relating to habitat of origin, invaded habitat, or in cases where multiple habitats are invaded.	No unique classification or ontology of habitats. Can be defined at different levels of resolution (e.g. "terrestrial" vs "calcareous Mediterranean grasslands") Could include the condition of habitat (degraded, restored, intact...)	Main entry point for scanning the literature for early careers	Wikidata Meta-analyses Early career
Taxonomic group of the invader	Taxonomic group of the invader.	different taxonomic resolutions, from coarse polyphyletic names (e.g. "Trees" or "Fish") to the precise sub-species. Synonyms and different taxonomies	Main entry point of lit search (e.g. for early career researchers) Main interest for managers	Wikidata ORKG Early career Freshwater biodiversity
Location	Location of the study sites Ideally very specific information up to the geographical coordinates	May be multiple and hierarchized Often imprecise in the paper (no geographical coordinates) different GIS reference systems: homogenize by using long_lat?	Entry point for literature search (managers,..) Scoping for meta-analysis	Meta-analyses Freshwater biodiversity

Study characteristics	Description and example	Particular issues?	Why is it useful?	Mentioned in break out groups
Data sets	Direct link to download open data supporting the paper, both underlying data and results. Should include description of datasets (metadata)	Not yet the norm but quickly changing When provided, datasets are not always complete/well described	Useful for meta-analyses aiming to re-analyse the data	Meta-analyses Early career Wikidata
Spatial scale	Spatial scale of the main phenomenon studied (e.g. invasion impact on a local community/landscape/global)	Sometimes difficult to define can be multiple and hierarchized Need to differentiate between grain and extent	scoping meta-analyses	Meta-analyses Early career
Temporal scale	Length of the dataset used in the study, or temporal scale of the phenomenon under study	may be multiple Both grain and extent Needs a unit	scoping meta-analyses	Meta-analyses
Approach	General methodological approach: experimental, observational, theoretical/mathematical	Should be very generic, but perhaps allow for hierarchical structure with a subcategory (e.g. experimental>greenhouse, or theoretical>simulations).	scoping meta-analyses Reviewing methodologies	Early career
Describing methods and results				
Methods	Methods used in the paper, which could be field (e.g. Braun-Blanquet vegetation cover assessment, Capture-Recapture), lab (e.g. AFLP sequencing) or statistical (e.g. Random Forests, GLMMs, etc.) methods.	standardisation of terms is not obvious, but will be necessary to be useful balance between generality and specify may be multiple and hierarchized by types A more precise description would provide a structure for reporting	scoping meta-analyses finding information about a methodology when early career	Meta-analyses Early career

Study characteristics	Description and example	Particular issues?	Why is it useful?	Mentioned in break out groups
		results=> metrics, units, and statistics		
Sample size	Number of replicated units of study	May be of different kinds (plots, species, individuals) Usually multiple and hierarchical: need an explicit data model to describe the study design	scoping and analysing meta-analyses	Meta-analyses
Sampling unit	Object or scale at which measurements are replicated, e.g. organ, individual, colony, population, plot, river, etc.	Very different kind of units are possible Some might need to be described by a unit of measurement (e.g. 5 m x 5m plots vs. 1Ha forest plots).	Scoping meta-analyses	Meta-analyses
Metrics	Which measurements were made or indices calculated?	Very heterogeneous Should be associated to a unit and a method	Meta-analyses Methodological reviews	Meta-analyses
Advanced concepts				
Hypothesis	Research hypothesis, as in Hi-Knowledge	There is no standardized way yet for describing hypotheses	Scoping meta-analyses Reviewing current support for the hypothesis Navigating hypotheses and finding knowledge gaps	Wikidata
Research question/Problem	Overall research question or problem that the study is trying to address. It is related to the research context (see below)	Genericity vs. Specificity Could be designed as a hierarchy	Entry point for managers Entry point for early career and anyone with new topic Navigating and finding quickly current answers to this problem in the literature (when crossed with other filters)	Wikidata Freshwater biodiversity
Index of controversy	An index describing whether a paper has encountered controversy	To be defined Cf. Scholia has a preliminary version of this	Evaluating the trustworthiness and importance of a piece of a theory or a result, especially for early career	Early career Wikidata

Study characteristics	Description and example	Particular issues?	Why is it useful?	Mentioned in break out groups
	since published (e.g. number of citations contradicting the paper, links to comments/responses at the time of publication).		Identifying research gaps and unresolved questions	
Research context/ Research field/school of thought	Overall research context or research field, e.g. conservation, theoretical community ecology, urban design, etc.	Difficult to find a classification of research fields which satisfies everyone May overlap with "Research Questions"?		Early career
Fundamental articles	Tag Identifying the most important articles in a field	Concept to be defined, probably manual annotation by the community, may be controversial Relies on defining the research field!	Entry point for early career	Early career
Theoretical commitments of the community/School of thought	Underlying paradigms, definitions and biases adopted by the group of authors	To be defined Authors may not explicitly admit to belonging to this school of thought Controversial May overlap with "Hypothesis".	Narrowing search when	Early career
Stage of invasion	Situating paper along stage of invasion => perhaps useful for refining the research question (what determines establishment? naturalization? invasiveness?)	Invasion is a gradual process. Also, papers may address several stages Papers may therefore be hard to classify	Scoping meta-analyses	Meta-analyses